

From Pseudorandom Play to Auditable Esports Competition: A Layered Randomness Infrastructure for Competitive Games

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Preprint — June 28, 2026

Working draft. Companion code : <https://github.com/thepriben/quantum-tetris>

Abstract

In video games, randomness is produced by invisible mechanisms — a seed, a pseudo-random generator, a probability table, a server call — whereas in physical games the draw has a visible, contestable “stage”. As soon as a game becomes a competition, and in esports in particular, this opacity ceases to be a mere design question and becomes a question of *integrity*: who generated the randomness, when, from which source, under which transformation, and with which verifiable guarantees? This paper argues that competitive games and cyber-physical competitions need an explicit *randomness infrastructure*, distinct from the statistical quality of the entropy source alone. Using the case study *Quantum Tetris* — a Tetris written in Rust/Bevy/WebAssembly whose stochastic decisions are delegated to simulated quantum circuits — we show that a good entropy source does not guarantee fairness: the bias of the “T” tetromino, induced by a 3-bit-to-7-piece mapping table, arises in the transformation layer and not in the source. We then decompose competitive randomness into six layers (entropy source, extraction, distribution policy, *mapping* function, cryptographic receipt, audit journal) and discuss the realistic contributions of quantum randomness (QRNG, certification via Bell-inequality violation) as well as the cryptographic tools of auditability (verifiable random functions, randomness beacons, verifiable delay functions, signed journals). We finally propose an architecture applicable to esports, competitive online games and *cyber-physical games* such as autonomous drone racing, and we implement its auditability layers in *Quantum Tetris* — hash-chained receipts and a commit-reveal journal — whose overhead we measure: on the order of a microsecond per draw, i.e. practically free auditability for a game of this class.

Keywords: randomness, verifiable randomness, esports, competitive integrity, quantum random number generators, cyber-physical games, Tetris, Rust, WebAssembly.

1 Introduction — from hidden randomness to competitive infrastructure

Randomness has an ancient place in games. It produces anticipation, surprise, replayability, sometimes frustration. It forces players to cope with a situation they do not fully control. Greg Costikyan describes uncertainty as one of the raw materials of game design: it gives games their tension, their variety and their ability to hold the player’s attention¹. In video games,

¹Greg Costikyan. *Uncertainty in Games*. Playful Thinking. Cambridge, MA: The MIT Press, 2013. ISBN: 9780262018968.

this uncertainty often rests on invisible mechanisms: a seed, a pseudo-random generator, a probability table, a server call. The player observes the outcome, rarely the protocol.

This invisibility transforms the social nature of randomness. In a physical game, the dice, the cards, the roulette wheel or the dice cup make the draw visible, manipulable and contestable by the participants. There, randomness has a stage. Players see the object, the gesture, the moment of the draw. In a digital game, this stage disappears behind the software engine. The random sequence may be statistically sound while remaining opaque. The problem then becomes less the existence of randomness than the trust placed in its production: who generated it, at what moment, with which source, under which transformation, and with which guarantees?

This question takes on particular importance in esports. Nicolas Besombes defines esports as a competitive practice of video gaming in which players confront one another, remotely or in person, in organized and regulated tournaments². From the moment a game becomes a competition, randomness enters a space of performance, ranking, refereeing, public broadcasting and sometimes economic stakes. A piece drawn in a competitive puzzle, a card dealt in a deck game, a zone generated in a battle royale or a loot table in a multiplayer game no longer belong to design alone. These events take part in the legitimacy of the result.

Physical games of chance have long developed devices to keep human intention at a distance. In the collective volume *Le hasard*, Olivier Caïra analyses the role of the dice cup: a simple but socially meaningful object that introduces a separation between the player's hand and the obtained result³. This separation does not mathematically prove the fairness of the draw. It makes the gesture more acceptable, because it reduces the visible possibility of manipulation. Digital competitions need software equivalents of such devices: mechanisms that make randomness not only unpredictable, but also explainable, traceable and verifiable.

The *Quantum Tetris* project is a minimal case study to explore this idea⁴. The game keeps a classic architecture: a board, pieces, a game loop, keyboard inputs, a scoring system, gravity, graphical rendering and a UI. It is developed in Rust with Bevy, can run as a native application and is also deployed in the browser via WebAssembly. The game's stochastic decisions go through a specialized layer able to run simulated quantum circuits. A measurement produces a bitstring, then this string is interpreted by the game engine. In the current version, circuits are simulated locally with RustQIP⁵; the architecture makes it possible to consider other backends, including a remote service, a quantum random number generator or a quantum machine accessible via API. A homonymous art project from an IBM × Parsons *design jam*⁶ also explores the mapping of quantum circuits to tetrominoes, but for aesthetic ends — celebrating the *noise* of present-day machines. Our case study pursues the opposite goal: not the aesthetics of noise, but the *auditability* and *fairness* of the randomness-production chain.

The architectural interest of *Quantum Tetris* lies in the separation between the game engine and the randomness source. The repository distinguishes a `game` crate, responsible for Tetris logic and Bevy systems, and a `quantum` crate, responsible for circuits, measurements, backends and simulators. Gameplay calls a common abstraction, `QuantumBackend::run(circuit) -> Measurement`, then decodes the bitstrings in the game logic⁷. The backend can change without

²Nicolas Besombes. “Les jeux vidéo compétitifs au prisme des jeux sportifs : du sport au sport électronique.” In: *Sciences du jeu* 5 (2016). DOI: [10.4000/sdj.612](https://doi.org/10.4000/sdj.612). URL: <http://journals.openedition.org/sdj/612>.

³Olivier Caïra. “Hasard et jeux.” In: *Le hasard*. Ed. by CNRS Éditions. Paris: CNRS Éditions, 2025. Chap. 6. ISBN: 978-2-271-15915-1. DOI: [10.4000/14b52](https://doi.org/10.4000/14b52).

⁴Benoît Prieur. *Quantum Tetris*. Dépôt logiciel, <https://github.com/thepriben/quantum-tetris>. Rust/Bevy/WebAssembly ; backends de simulation de circuits quantiques. 2026; Benoît Prieur. “Quantum Tetris : Rust, Bevy, WebAssembly et circuits quantiques dans la boucle de jeu.” In: *Programmez!* (2026). Hors-série n° 23, pp. 7–11.

⁵Sumner Roetteler and contributors. *RustQIP: a flexible quantum computing simulator written in Rust*. Bibliothèque logicielle (crate `qip`), <https://github.com/Renmusxd/RustQIP>. 2024.

⁶Weijing Xiao et al. *Quantum Tetris*. <https://olivierbrcknr.github.io/quantum-tetris/>. Quantum Design Jam, Parsons School of Design & IBM, New York City. 2021.

⁷Prieur, *Quantum Tetris*.

rewriting the rules of Tetris. This separation offers an experimental ground to compare several randomness sources, study their distributions, measure their latency and add proofs or audit journals.

The project also brings out a deep difficulty: a good-quality entropy source does not by itself guarantee a fair distribution in the game. This is the central argument of this paper, summarized by the formula *entropy is not fairness*. Quantum randomness fits into this chain as a physical entropy source. Quantum random number generators (QRNGs) exploit measured quantum phenomena to produce random bits. Herrero-Collantes and García-Escartín present them as one of the most mature quantum technologies, with established uses in simulation, cryptography and engineering⁸. For competitive games, the most plausible medium-term hypothesis is not a game running entirely on a universal quantum computer, but a quantum entropy layer, local or remote, integrated into an audit protocol. To remove any ambiguity: this paper does not argue that esports need quantum computers, but that competitive games need *auditable* randomness infrastructures, in which quantum entropy may occupy a single layer.

This problem goes beyond strictly digital games. Cyber-physical competitions — autonomous drone racing, competitive robotics, artificial-intelligence agents in physical or simulated environments — also rest on rules, courses, constraints and challenge conditions⁹. A controlled and auditable randomization could serve to generate variations of course, of gates or of trial conditions after the agents are submitted, in order to reduce excessive adaptation to a fixed environment while guaranteeing that all competitors are subject to the same protocol.

Contribution. The contribution of this paper is fourfold. First, it proposes to treat competitive randomness as a *trust infrastructure* rather than a mere software primitive. Second, it analyses *Quantum Tetris* as a software case study, showing how a classic game engine can delegate its stochastic decisions to an interchangeable layer. Third, it uses the bias of the “T” tetromino to rigorously distinguish entropy, *mapping* and fairness. Fourth, it proposes a six-layer *randomness infrastructure* architecture, applicable to esports, competitive online games and *cyber-physical games*, where QRNGs, verifiable random functions, randomness beacons, signed journals and distribution policies can be combined; it provides a reference implementation of the two auditability layers in *Quantum Tetris* — hash-chained receipts, a commit-reveal journal and an offline verifier — whose overhead it measures.

Nature of the article. This paper assumes an explicit status: it is an argued *perspective*, backed by a software case study and a measurement of the audit overhead, rather than an empirical field study or a large-scale governance analysis. Its contribution is conceptual (an analytical framework for competitive integrity) and demonstrative (a measured artefact), not statistical or ethnographic. This scoping guides the choice of presented elements and the limits discussed in Section 10.

Outline. Section 2 revisits the role of randomness and uncertainty in video games. Section 3 examines the status of randomness in esports and online competitions. Section 4 presents *Quantum Tetris* as a software laboratory. Section 5 analyses the *mapping* problem from the case of the “T” tetromino. Section 6 discusses the cryptographic tools of auditability. Section 7 specifies the realistic contributions of quantum randomness. Section 8 proposes a general auditable-randomness infrastructure, implements and evaluates its auditability layers, then derives its applications. Sections 9 and 10 present a threat model and the limits of the approach, before the conclusion (Section 11).

⁸Miguel Herrero-Collantes and Juan Carlos García-Escartín. “Quantum random number generators.” In: *Reviews of Modern Physics* 89.1 (2017), p. 015004. DOI: [10.1103/RevModPhys.89.015004](https://doi.org/10.1103/RevModPhys.89.015004).

⁹Elia Kaufmann et al. “Champion-level drone racing using deep reinforcement learning.” In: *Nature* 620.7976 (2023), pp. 982–987. DOI: [10.1038/s41586-023-06419-4](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41586-023-06419-4); Philipp Foehn et al. “AlphaPilot: Autonomous drone racing.” In: *Autonomous Robots* 46.1 (2022), pp. 307–320. DOI: [10.1007/s10514-021-10011-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s10514-021-10011-y).

Related work. Several communities have addressed fragments of this problem without treating it as a unified infrastructure for competition. Online gambling popularized *provably fair* schemes, based on committing then revealing seeds¹⁰. Distributed cryptography produced public, bias-resistant randomness beacons¹¹, verifiable random functions¹² and verifiable delay functions¹³. Video-game research theorized uncertainty as a design resource¹⁴ and procedural content generation¹⁵. Quantum physics established randomness generators up to certification via Bell-inequality violation¹⁶. Finally, robotics resorts to domain randomization for generalization¹⁷. Our contribution invents none of these primitives: it articulates them into a six-layer chain dedicated to *competitive integrity*, and shows, through the case of the “T” tetromino, why none of them suffices in isolation.

2 Randomness and uncertainty in video games

Uncertainty is not a flaw of a game: it is often its engine. Costikyan distinguishes several sources of uncertainty — performance uncertainty, opponent uncertainty, randomness uncertainty, hidden-information uncertainty — and shows that a game without any uncertainty loses most of its interest¹⁸. Randomness is one of these sources, and it interacts with the others: a random draw creates hidden information, modifies the decision space and redistributes advantage.

Roger Caillois had proposed a famous typology of games, opposing in particular *agon* (competition based on merit and skill) to *alea* (the game of chance, where the player relies on fate)¹⁹. Caïra proposes to go beyond this overly sharp opposition: in real play practices, chance does not erase decision, and skill does not exclude letting go²⁰. The dice cup illustrates this point perfectly. It does not make the die “more random” in the mathematical sense; it makes the draw *socially acceptable* by interposing a visible barrier between the hand and the result. The value of the device is procedural and social as much as statistical.

It is precisely this procedural dimension that is lost in digital play. A pseudo-random generator (PRNG) produces a deterministic sequence from a seed; its statistical quality is measured

¹⁰Manuel Blum. “Coin Flipping by Telephone: A Protocol for Solving Impossible Problems.” In: *ACM SIGACT News* 15.1 (1983), pp. 23–27. DOI: [10.1145/1008908.1008911](https://doi.org/10.1145/1008908.1008911).

¹¹Ewa Syta et al. “Scalable Bias-Resistant Distributed Randomness.” In: *2017 IEEE Symposium on Security and Privacy (SP)*. 2017, pp. 444–460. DOI: [10.1109/SP.2017.45](https://doi.org/10.1109/SP.2017.45); John Kelsey et al. *A Reference for Randomness Beacons: Format and Protocol Version 2*. NIST Internal Report NISTIR 8213 (Draft). National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), 2019. DOI: [10.6028/NIST.IR.8213-draft](https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.IR.8213-draft); Joseph Bonneau, Jeremy Clark, and Steven Goldfeder. *On Bitcoin as a public randomness source*. Cryptology ePrint Archive, Report 2015/1015. 2015. URL: <https://eprint.iacr.org/2015/1015>.

¹²Silvio Micali, Michael Rabin, and Salil Vadhan. “Verifiable Random Functions.” In: *Proceedings of the 40th Annual Symposium on Foundations of Computer Science (FOCS)*. 1999, pp. 120–130. DOI: [10.1109/SFCS.1999.814584](https://doi.org/10.1109/SFCS.1999.814584); Sharon Goldberg et al. *Verifiable Random Functions (VRFs)*. RFC 9381. Internet Research Task Force (IRTF), 2023. DOI: [10.17487/RFC9381](https://doi.org/10.17487/RFC9381).

¹³Dan Boneh et al. “Verifiable Delay Functions.” In: *Advances in Cryptology – CRYPTO 2018*. Vol. 10991. LNCS. Springer, 2018, pp. 757–788. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-96884-1_25](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-96884-1_25).

¹⁴Costikyan, *Uncertainty in Games*.

¹⁵Noor Shaker, Julian Togelius, and Mark J. Nelson. *Procedural Content Generation in Games*. Springer, 2016. DOI: [10.1007/978-3-319-42716-4](https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-319-42716-4).

¹⁶Herrero-Collantes and García-Escartín, “Quantum random number generators”; S. Pironio et al. “Random numbers certified by Bell’s theorem.” In: *Nature* 464.7291 (2010), pp. 1021–1024. DOI: [10.1038/nature09008](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature09008); Antonio Acín and Lluís Masanes. “Certified randomness in quantum physics.” In: *Nature* 540.7632 (2016), pp. 213–219. DOI: [10.1038/nature20119](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature20119).

¹⁷Josh Tobin et al. “Domain randomization for transferring deep neural networks from simulation to the real world.” In: *2017 IEEE/RSJ International Conference on Intelligent Robots and Systems (IROS)*. 2017, pp. 23–30. DOI: [10.1109/IROS.2017.8202133](https://doi.org/10.1109/IROS.2017.8202133).

¹⁸Costikyan, *Uncertainty in Games*.

¹⁹Roger Caillois. *Les jeux et les hommes : le masque et le vertige*. Paris: Gallimard, 1958.

²⁰Caïra, “Hasard et jeux.”

by test batteries²¹, and its cryptographic quality depends on the unpredictability of the seed and of the internal state²². But none of these properties says *who* controls the seed, *when* the draw took place, nor whether the transformation of bits into a game event is honest. A sequence can pass all statistical tests and remain manipulable by whoever chooses the seed or observes the state in advance.

Procedural content generation (PCG) adds a further layer: levels, maps, loot and opponents are shaped by algorithms parameterized by randomness²³. In a single-player context, the opacity of these mechanisms is inconsequential; the player accepts the result. In a competitive context, by contrast, each draw becomes a potentially contestable element of the sporting result. It is this shift from *design* to *refereeing* that justifies rethinking randomness as an infrastructure.

3 The status of randomness in esports and online competitions

Esports shares four structuring traits with sport: it is a motor, competitive, codified and institutionalized situation²⁴. Codification implies explicit rules and refereeing; institutionalization implies organizers, rankings and stakes. Yet, in video games, part of the rules is buried in the software: the dual regulatory frame of esports is at once that of the organizers and that, opaque, of the game's code. Randomness sits at this border.

Three developments make the question urgent today. First, *professionalization*: prize pools, salaries and transfers turn a contested draw into an economic stake, no longer merely a ludic one. Second, *broadcasting* and associated betting, which expose every result to a wide audience and to third-party financial interests. Third, the *regulatory attention* paid to randomness in games — the framing of loot boxes in several jurisdictions is its most visible sign, following work showing their psychological proximity to gambling²⁵. In this context, the inability to prove after the fact that a draw was not skewed is no longer a technical detail: it is a concrete risk for organizers and players alike.

Several competitive genres rest centrally on draws: card distribution in collectible card games, loot tables in shooters, zone generation in battle royales, or the sequence of pieces in puzzle games. When a title becomes the medium of regulated competition, the integrity of these draws is no longer a private matter between the publisher and the player: it conditions the public legitimacy of the result. Holden, Kaburakis and Rodenberg stress that esports, as it professionalizes, inherits integrity issues well known to sport — cheating, result manipulation, conflicts of interest — but in a setting where control tools and regulation remain immature²⁶. A recent systematic review of the esports-integrity literature confirms this diagnosis: the field remains fragmented, and the design and enforcement of regulatory policies stand out as a major research avenue²⁷.

Concretely, the points where randomness touches competitive integrity are many and already sources of litigation or suspicion: the order of distribution and the shuffle in card games; loot

²¹Andrew Rukhin, Juan Soto, James Nechvatal, et al. *A Statistical Test Suite for Random and Pseudorandom Number Generators for Cryptographic Applications*. Special Publication 800-22 Rev. 1a. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), 2010. DOI: [10.6028/NIST.SP.800-22r1a](https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.800-22r1a).

²²Meltem Sönmez Turan et al. *Recommendation for the Entropy Sources Used for Random Bit Generation*. Special Publication 800-90B. National Institute of Standards and Technology (NIST), 2018. DOI: [10.6028/NIST.SP.800-90B](https://doi.org/10.6028/NIST.SP.800-90B).

²³Shaker, Togelius, and Nelson, *Procedural Content Generation in Games*.

²⁴Besombes, “Les jeux vidéo compétitifs au prisme des jeux sportifs : du sport au sport électronique.”

²⁵Aaron Drummond and James D. Sauer. “Video game loot boxes are psychologically akin to gambling.” In: *Nature Human Behaviour* 2.8 (2018), pp. 530–532. DOI: [10.1038/s41562-018-0360-1](https://doi.org/10.1038/s41562-018-0360-1).

²⁶John T. Holden, Anastasios Kaburakis, and Ryan M. Rodenberg. “The Future is Now: Esports Policy Considerations and Potential Litigation.” In: *Journal of Legal Aspects of Sport* 27.1 (2017), pp. 46–78. DOI: [10.1123/jlas.2016-0018](https://doi.org/10.1123/jlas.2016-0018).

²⁷Erika Riedl and Pim Verschuuren. “A systematic literature review of esports integrity.” In: *The International Sports Law Journal* 25 (2025), pp. 99–118. DOI: [10.1007/s40318-025-00295-y](https://doi.org/10.1007/s40318-025-00295-y).

tables and the opening of chests (loot boxes), whose random nature has prompted regulatory frameworks in several countries; the map-generation seed or the zone trajectory in battle royales; matchmaking and the assignment of sides or maps in tournaments. In each of these cases, the player undergoes a draw that they can neither observe nor replay. The relevant question is then not so much “was the draw uniform?” as “can one prove, after the fact, that it was not skewed in favour of one party?”

The emblematic case is the Tetris piece generator. Modern implementations generally use a so-called “7-bag” system: the seven tetrominoes are placed in a bag, shuffled, then dealt one by one until exhausted before a new bag is formed²⁸. This mechanism is not a simple uniform draw: it is a *distribution policy*. It bounds predictability (one cannot receive the same piece three times in a row across two bags beyond a certain limit), guarantees the balance of the seven pieces over a short window, and shapes the players’ perception of fairness. Two competitors playing different seeds do not receive the same sequence, but they are subject to the same *policy*. Competitive fairness is thus decided less at the bit level than at the level of the distribution rule and its verifiability.

In the online gambling sector, a partial answer has emerged under the name “provably fair”: the server commits in advance to a seed by publishing its hash (commitment), the client provides its own seed, and the server’s seed is revealed a posteriori to allow verification of the draw. This commit-reveal scheme derives directly from Blum’s coin-flipping-by-telephone protocol²⁹. It does not make the draw “more random”; it makes it *auditable*. Online gambling developed these procedural guarantees because money makes every draw contestable; esports, as it professionalizes, reaches the same point of maturity. This is exactly the kind of guarantee it needs, and which Section 6 generalizes.

4 Quantum Tetris: a software laboratory

Quantum Tetris is a playable Tetris whose stochastic events — active piece, spawn orientation and column, fall cadence, placement bonus, score multiplier — are driven, by default, by the measurement of quantum circuits³⁰. The player keeps control of movement; the game draws everything else from circuit measurements. The engine is written in Rust with Bevy and compiles both as a native binary and to WebAssembly for the browser.

4.1 An architecture with separated layers

The repository explicitly separates three responsibilities: the *game engine* (crate `game`, Tetris logic and Bevy systems), the *quantum layer* (crate `quantum`: intermediate representation of circuits, gates, measurements and backends) and the *tooling* (circuit-diagram rendering, WebAssembly build, deployment). The core of this design is a single abstraction: the game never directly calls a generator, but invokes

```
QuantumBackend::run(circuit) → Measurement,
```

then decodes the bitstrings in a dedicated module (`measurement_fx.rs`). Changing backend never modifies the rules of Tetris³¹.

Two backends coexist. The *Classic* backend produces uniformly random bits (`rand`) and serves as a reference without a simulator. The *RustQIP* backend runs, in memory, a statevector simulation of the same circuits, on desktop as in the browser³². The same gate set therefore

²⁸Tetris Wiki. *Random Generator (7-bag)*. https://tetris.wiki/Random_Generator. Consulté en 2026. 2023.

²⁹Blum, “Coin Flipping by Telephone: A Protocol for Solving Impossible Problems.”

³⁰Prieur, *Quantum Tetris*; Prieur, “Quantum Tetris : Rust, Bevy, WebAssembly et circuits quantiques dans la boucle de jeu.”

³¹Prieur, *Quantum Tetris*.

³²Roetteler and contributors, *RustQIP: a flexible quantum computing simulator written in Rust*.

produces the same theoretical distributions regardless of the platform. This interchangeability is the project’s first methodological lesson: *the randomness source is a replaceable component, not a fixed property of the game.*

4.2 Circuits as event sources

Five circuit presets feed the gameplay (Table 1). At each piece spawn, three measurements follow in sequence: a 3-bit draw chooses the tetromino, a 2-bit circuit fixes the orientation and column, another fixes the gravity interval. The space bar triggers an additional measurement (placement bonus), and each completed line triggers another (score multiplier).

Circuit	Qubits	When	Game effect
quantum-teleportation-gate-v1	3	spawn	tetromino choice
imp-brain-v1	2	spawn	rotation (0-3) + column
enemy-profile-hunter-v1	2	spawn	gravity interval
observation-pulse-v1	2	Space	placement bonus (hard drop)
q-shard-stabilizer-v1	2	line clear	multiplier ($\times 1$ to $\times 4$)

Table 1: Correspondence between circuits and gameplay events in *Quantum Tetris*.

For illustration, Figure 1 reproduces the quantum-teleportation-gate-v1 circuit as defined in the repository³³: it is the one that produces the three bits subsequently mapped onto a tetromino (Section 5). Inspired by the teleportation protocol, it prepares a “message” qubit through an R_y rotation, creates an entangled pair, then performs the sender-side measurement; the three output bits, which in the academic protocol would serve as classical corrections, are here directly exposed as game state.

Figure 1: The quantum-teleportation-gate-v1 circuit (3 qubits) used for tetromino choice. Measuring the three qubits yields a 3-bit string, then mapped onto one of the seven pieces by the *mapping* table of Table 2. The diagram reproduces the effective gate sequence of the repository.

The point of this device is not to claim that Tetris becomes “quantum” in the sense of a computational advantage. It is to materialize, in a playable and minimal system, the complete chain that goes from a physical entropy source (simulated here) to an observable game event. This chain is exactly where the questions of fairness and audit reside.

5 The *mapping* problem: the case of the “T” tetromino

The quantum-teleportation-gate-v1 circuit produces three bits, i.e. eight equiprobable outcomes under a uniform distribution: 000, 001, ..., 111. But Tetris has only seven tetrominoes: I, O, T, S, Z, J and L. A mapping function from eight strings to seven pieces is therefore required. The table currently implemented is reproduced in Table 2.

³³Prieur, *Quantum Tetris*.

000	001	010	011	100	101	110	111
I	O	T	S	Z	J	L	T

Table 2: 3-bit \rightarrow tetromino *mapping* table. The eighth outcome 111 is folded onto T.

Under a uniform distribution of the eight strings, each string has probability $1/8$. The pieces I, O, S, Z, J and L each receive one outcome, hence a probability $1/8$. The T piece receives two outcomes (010 and 111), hence a probability $2/8 = 1/4$. The effective distribution of pieces is thus

$$P(\text{T}) = \frac{1}{4}, \quad P(X) = \frac{1}{8} \text{ for } X \in \{\text{I, O, S, Z, J, L}\},$$

i.e. a T tetromino drawn twice as often as any other piece. This result is analytical and is verified empirically: by sampling the circuit a large number of times, with the *Classic* backend as with the *RustQIP* backend, the observed frequency of the T piece converges to $1/4$ and that of the six others to $1/8$. The bias is therefore a property of the table, independent of the backend.

Where is the bias born? This bias does not come from the entropy source. Whether the bits are produced by `rand`, by a RustQIP simulation or, tomorrow, by a perfectly uniform physical QRNG, the T piece would remain over-represented, because the imbalance is introduced by the *mapping function*, that is, by the transformation layer that projects a space of eight states onto seven events. This is the heart of the argument: **an impeccable entropy source is not enough to guarantee a fair distribution of game events**. Fairness is a property of the complete *chain*, not of the source alone.

Three ways to correct. The T case also illustrates that there are several correction policies, and that the choice between them is an act of design, not an automatism. (i) *Rejection* (rejection sampling): the eighth outcome is removed, restoring uniformity at the price of a variable cost (sometimes one must redraw). (ii) The *bag policy* (“7-bag”): the raw piece-by-piece draw is no longer used, but a random permutation of the seven pieces, which bounds predictability and guarantees balance over a short window³⁴. (iii) *Assumed and documented bias*: the over-representation of T is kept as a game-design choice, provided it is made public and verifiable. These three options are legitimate; what is not, in a competitive context, is an *undocumented* bias that players undergo without being able to observe it.

Between the bits and the game event, three things are therefore needed: an explicit *distribution policy*, a *public documentation* of that policy, and, in competitive contexts, an *audit possibility*. Raw randomness produces bits; the game produces events; the justice of the result is decided in the space that separates them.

6 Cryptographic tools of auditability

If fairness is a property of the chain, tools are needed to make it verifiable end to end. Modern cryptography provides several, complementary ones.

Commitment and reveal (commit-reveal). The simplest scheme. A party publishes the hash of a secret value before the draw (commitment), then reveals the value afterwards. Anyone can then recompute the draw and verify that it matches the initial commitment. This protocol, stemming from Blum’s coin flip³⁵, underpins “provably fair” schemes and often combines a server seed and a client seed so that neither party alone controls the result.

³⁴Tetris Wiki, *Random Generator (7-bag)*.

³⁵Blum, “Coin Flipping by Telephone: A Protocol for Solving Impossible Problems.”

Verifiable random functions (VRF). A VRF is the public-key version of a keyed hash function: only the holder of the secret key can compute the output, but anyone with the public key can verify that it is correct³⁶. The output is both *pseudo-random* and *provable*: it comes with a compact proof. The IRTF standardized RSA and elliptic-curve constructions in RFC 9381³⁷. For a competitive game, a VRF lets a server draw a sequence deterministically from a game identifier, while providing each player with a verifiable proof that the sequence was not chosen after the fact.

Randomness beacons. A beacon publishes, at regular intervals, public and timestamped random values, accompanied by integrity guarantees. NIST specifies the format and protocol³⁸. A decentralized, bias-resistant version can be obtained through threshold protocols where no participant controls the output, such as *RandHound/RandHerd*³⁹. One can also derive public randomness from a blockchain, with due precautions regarding manipulability by miners⁴⁰. A beacon provides a common temporal reference: all competitors in a tournament can share the same public source, which eliminates the suspicion of “tailor-made” seeds.

Verifiable delay functions (VDF). A VDF imposes an incompressible sequential computation time to produce its output, while making the latter quickly verifiable⁴¹. It prevents an actor from “replaying” or anticipating a draw faster than expected, and serves notably to harden beacons against last-minute manipulation (an actor cannot compute the output in advance to choose whether or not to contribute to it).

Signed journals and timestamping. Finally, the signed and timestamped record of each draw — source used, raw bits, applied policy, resulting event — constitutes an *audit journal*. Combined with the primitives above, it allows post-match verification: reconstruct the game, recompute each event, and prove that the announced protocol was indeed followed.

None of these primitives makes randomness “better” in the statistical sense. All make it *accountable*: traceable, attributable, verifiable. This is the software translation of the dice cup.

7 Realistic contributions of quantum randomness

Quantum randomness intervenes in this chain at the level of the *entropy source*, and possibly of its *certification*. One must carefully separate what quantum technology really brings from what it does not.

Entropy of physical origin. Quantum random number generators (QRNG) exploit the fundamental indeterminism of quantum measurement — photon arrival times, shot noise, vacuum fluctuations — to produce bits whose unpredictability does not rest on a computational-complexity assumption, unlike PRNGs. Herrero-Collantes and García-Escartín offer a detailed review and rank them among the most mature quantum technologies, already commercialized⁴².

Certifiable entropy. Quantum technology additionally allows a guarantee inaccessible to the classical world: the *certification* of randomness. Relying on the violation of a Bell inequality, one can prove that an output contains genuine randomness *without making any assumption about*

³⁶Micali, Rabin, and Vadhan, “Verifiable Random Functions.”

³⁷Goldberg et al., *Verifiable Random Functions (VRFs)*.

³⁸Kelsey et al., *A Reference for Randomness Beacons: Format and Protocol Version 2*.

³⁹Syta et al., “Scalable Bias-Resistant Distributed Randomness.”

⁴⁰Bonneau, Clark, and Goldfeder, *On Bitcoin as a public randomness source*.

⁴¹Boneh et al., “Verifiable Delay Functions.”

⁴²Herrero-Collantes and García-Escartín, “Quantum random number generators.”

the internal workings of the device (device-independent scenario). Pironio *et al.* gave a proof of principle⁴³, since formalized under the name *certified randomness*⁴⁴ and made more robust by loophole-free Bell tests⁴⁵. This is conceptually the strongest analogue of the dice cup: not only is the draw unpredictable, but this unpredictability is *proved* to a third party, even if the hardware is supplied by an adversary.

What quantum technology does not bring. A QRNG, even certified, solves neither the *mapping* problem (the T-tetromino bias would persist) nor that of *chain* auditability (who applied which policy, when). An opaque QRNG remains a black box: it provides high-quality bits, but without a receipt or journal it brings no competitive-integrity guarantee superior to that of a good PRNG combined with a VRF. The value of quantum technology is therefore *conditional*: it materializes when it is integrated into a protocol of proof, public *mapping* and post-match verification. For competitive games, the realistic medium-term hypothesis is not a fully quantum game, but a *quantum entropy layer* — local or exposed as a service — plugged into the QuantumBackend abstraction of *Quantum Tetris*, alongside the classic and simulated backends.

8 An auditable randomness infrastructure

The previous sections converge toward a simple thesis: competitive randomness must be thought of as an *infrastructure* composed of distinct layers, each carrying its own guarantees. We distinguish six.

- C1. Entropy source** — the physical or algorithmic origin of the bits: seeded PRNG, CSPRNG, QRNG, certified QRNG. Targeted guarantee: unpredictability.
- C2. Extraction / processing** — conditioning and extraction of uniform randomness from possibly biased raw bits, with entropy assessment⁴⁶ and statistical tests⁴⁷. Guarantee: statistical quality.
- C3. Distribution policy** — the rule that turns randomness into the intended distribution: uniform draw, rejection, “7-bag”, weightings⁴⁸. Guarantee: structural fairness and bounded predictability.
- C4. Mapping function** — the final projection onto game events (the T case, Section 5). Guarantee: absence of undocumented bias.
- C5. Cryptographic receipt** — commitment, VRF proof or beacon reference, attesting that a given draw was fixed before the event⁴⁹. Guarantee: non-repudiation and anti-anticipation.
- C6. Audit journal** — signed and timestamped record of the whole chain, enabling reconstruction and post-match verification. Guarantee: end-to-end traceability.

⁴³Pironio *et al.*, “Random numbers certified by Bell’s theorem.”

⁴⁴Acín and Masanes, “Certified randomness in quantum physics.”

⁴⁵B. Hensen *et al.* “Loophole-free Bell inequality violation using electron spins separated by 1.3 kilometres.” In: *Nature* 526.7575 (2015), pp. 682–686. DOI: [10.1038/nature15759](https://doi.org/10.1038/nature15759).

⁴⁶Turan *et al.*, *Recommendation for the Entropy Sources Used for Random Bit Generation*.

⁴⁷Rukhin, Soto, Nechvatal, *et al.*, *A Statistical Test Suite for Random and Pseudorandom Number Generators for Cryptographic Applications*.

⁴⁸Tetris Wiki, *Random Generator (7-bag)*.

⁴⁹Micali, Rabin, and Vadhan, “Verifiable Random Functions”; Goldberg *et al.*, *Verifiable Random Functions (VRFs)*; Kelsey *et al.*, *A Reference for Randomness Beacons: Format and Protocol Version 2*; Boneh *et al.*, “Verifiable Delay Functions.”

This decomposition has a diagnostic virtue: it allows one to locate precisely *where* an integrity problem sits. The T-tetromino bias is a defect of **C4**, not of **C1**. A seed chosen by a dishonest server is a defect of **C5**. A tournament where competitors receive different conditions without justification is a defect of **C3**. Quantum technology strengthens **C1** (and possibly the associated certification), but dispenses with none of the other layers.

Quantum Tetris materializes the six layers at the scale of a case study. It carries **C1** (interchangeable backends), **C3** and **C4** (explicit policies and *mapping* in `measurement_fx.rs`), and implements a concrete instance of **C5** and **C6**: each draw produces a hash-chained receipt, recorded in a commit-reveal audit journal, without affecting the Tetris logic⁵⁰.

8.1 A verifiable instance of layers C5 and C6

The `QuantumBackend::run` abstraction provides the natural insertion point of the two auditability layers. The repository offers a direct realization, based solely on standard primitives (SHA-256 and commit-reveal), articulated in three steps.

Commitment (before the game). At the opening of a session, a seed is drawn and only its hash SHA-256(seed) is published as a *commitment*, before any draw. A *genesis hash* binds this commitment to the session’s identity and to the announced policies:

$$h_0 = \text{SHA-256}(\text{genesis} \parallel \text{session} \parallel \text{commitment} \parallel \text{backend} \parallel \text{pol.}_{\text{C3}} \parallel \text{pol.}_{\text{C4}}).$$

Chained receipt (at each draw — C5). Each draw of rank n adds an entry (rank, game moment, circuit, measured bits, decoded effect, backend) and a receipt that chains it to the previous one:

$$h_n = \text{SHA-256}(\text{entry} \parallel h_{n-1} \parallel n \parallel \text{moment} \parallel \text{circuit} \parallel \text{bits} \parallel \text{effect} \parallel \text{backend}).$$

Any alteration of a field breaks the chain from the rank concerned onward.

Reveal and verification (after the game — C6). At the end of the session, the seed is revealed and the complete journal — metadata, entries and chain head — is exported as append-only JSON (Figure 2). An offline verifier recomputes the chain and checks that SHA-256(revealed seed) equals the initial commitment; a zero exit code attests to the integrity of the game.

This realization is one *instance* among others. The committed seed can be replaced by the output of a VRF or the value of a public beacon (Section 6) without changing the journal’s structure, and a QRNG can feed the entropy step without touching layers C5–C6. Verifiable delay functions and full VRF proofs are not yet wired in: they constitute direct substitutes for the commitment.

```
{
  "seq": 1,
  "moment": "spawn_piece",
  "circuit": "quantum-teleportation-gate-v1",
  "bits": "111",
  "effect": "piece=T",
  "backend_used": "rustqip",
  "entry_hash": "d4e5f6..."
}
```

Figure 2: One entry of the audit journal (**C6**): the draw produces the string 111, mapped onto the T piece (Table 2), and the receipt `entry_hash` (**C5**) chains the entry to the previous one.

⁵⁰Prieur, *Quantum Tetris*.

8.2 Evaluation of the audit overhead

Making a game verifiable has a cost, which can be measured. Table 3 reports indicative measurements obtained on the quantum crate, in optimized compilation and on a single core (Apple Silicon processor), averaged over 2×10^5 draws.

Measurement	Value
Draw — Classic backend (uniform RNG)	$\approx 0.5 \mu\text{s}$
Draw — RustQIP backend (3-qubit circuit)	$\approx 0.19 \text{ ms}$
Audit overhead per draw (C5 receipt + C6 journal)	$\approx 2.2 \mu\text{s}$
Offline verification	$\approx 2.1 \mu\text{s}/\text{entry}$
Journal size (compact JSON)	$\approx 216 \text{ bytes}/\text{entry}$
~ 10 min match (≈ 1800 draws)	$\approx 4 \text{ ms CPU}, \approx 380 \text{ KiB}$

Table 3: Overhead of the auditability layers (C5, C6) in *Quantum Tetris*. Indicative measurements (optimized compilation, single core, averaged over 2×10^5 draws); a controlled cross-platform benchmark is left to future work.

Two lessons emerge. On the one hand, the marginal overhead of the auditability layers — about $2 \mu\text{s}$ per draw — is nearly four orders of magnitude below the budget of a frame at 60 Hz (16.7 ms), and remains even below the cost of a simulated quantum draw ($\approx 0.19 \text{ ms}$); recording a draw verifiably therefore costs less than the draw itself. A complete game of about ten minutes accumulates on the order of 4 ms of audit computation and a journal of a few hundred kilobytes, verifiable offline in well under a second. For a game of this class, **auditability is essentially free**. On the other hand, the often-invoked “real-time” tension does not manifest here: it would become noticeable only at much higher draw rates, or with proofs costly per draw (typically a VDF), which is a matter of sizing and not a fundamental obstacle.

8.3 Applications to esports and competitive online games

In a tournament, one can imagine the following scheme. Before the game, the organizer publishes the distribution policy (C3, C4) and commits to a source: either a public beacon common to all competitors⁵¹, or a VRF whose public key is known⁵². During the game, each draw is derived from this source and accompanied by a receipt (C5). After the game, the journal (C6) lets a referee, an opponent or the public replay the sequence and verify that no step was altered. Randomness then ceases to be an argument from authority (“the server drew”) and becomes a verifiable fact.

Who uses the audit? This mechanism only makes sense once one specifies *who* uses it, and how. A single journal serves several actors with distinct interests. The *organizer* publishes the policies and the commitment before the game (C3–C5), thereby putting its accountability on the line. The *referee* (or integrity committee) replays the journal in case of a complaint and rules on a verifiable rather than declarative basis (C6). The *player* or their team can contest a draw by recomputing the sequence, without having to trust the publisher. The *public* and *commentators* have public proof, which defuses live suspicion. The *publisher* and the *platform* provide the implementation and retain the journals as evidence. Finally, a *regulator* or a *sponsor* may require auditability as a condition of certification, accreditation or funding. Auditability is therefore not merely a technical property: it is a *governance device* that shifts the burden of

⁵¹Kelsey et al., *A Reference for Randomness Beacons: Format and Protocol Version 2*; Syta et al., “Scalable Bias-Resistant Distributed Randomness.”

⁵²Goldberg et al., *Verifiable Random Functions (VRFs)*.

proof, from “trust us” toward “verify for yourself”, and explicitly distributes roles among the stakeholders of a competition.

Example of an auditable draw (piece sequence). Concretely, the tetromino draw can become verifiable as follows:

1. **Before the game**, the organizer publishes the distribution policy (for example the “7-bag”) and the public key of its VRF, or else the identifier of a public beacon common to all competitors.
2. **At the start of the game**, a master seed is fixed: either the value of the beacon at an agreed instant, or the VRF output evaluated on the game identifier, together with its proof.
3. **At each draw**, piece number n is derived from the master seed and from n by a public function, then projected onto a piece by the announced policy. The proof guarantees that the value was not chosen after the fact.
4. **After the game**, the signed journal — seed, proofs, policy, events — is published. Anyone replays the sequence and verifies that each piece indeed follows from the announced protocol.

The same mechanism accommodates a quantum entropy layer: a QRNG, local or exposed as a service, feeds step 2, and its receipt takes its place in the journal of step 4.

8.4 Cyber-physical applications: autonomous drone racing

Cyber-physical competitions offer a particularly interesting ground. In autonomous drone racing, agents must traverse at high speed a sequence of gates, relying solely on onboard sensors and limited compute; systems such as *Swift*⁵³ or *AlphaPilot*⁵⁴ have reached a competitive level against human pilots. A major sporting risk, in this setting, is *overfitting* to a fixed course: an agent optimized for a precise layout no longer measures a general flying competence.

Domain randomization is already used in training to favour generalization from simulation to reality⁵⁵. An auditable randomness infrastructure would make it possible to turn it into a *trial instrument*: generating, *after* the agents are submitted, variations of course, of gate positions or of conditions (simulated wind, lighting) from a public source committed in advance (**C1**, **C5**), according to an announced policy (**C3**), with a verifiable journal (**C6**). One thus obtains two simultaneous guarantees: competitors cannot over-fit a course known in advance, and all are subject to exactly the same protocol, which is verifiable after the trial. The same logic extends to competitive robotics and to agent competitions in simulated environments.

9 Threat model

To specify what the infrastructure protects, we distinguish several adversaries. **(A) The dishonest operator** controls the server and could choose the seed, replay an unfavourable draw or change the policy mid-game; **C5** (commitment/VRF) and **C6** (journal) neutralize it by making every draw fixed in advance and verifiable. **(B) The cheating player** seeks to predict future draws; **C1** (an unpredictable source, ideally certified) and the use of a VDF⁵⁶ prevent anticipation. **(C) The hardware supplier** could deliver a biased or “rigged” QRNG; device-independent certification⁵⁷ answers precisely this threat by avoiding any assumption of trust

⁵³Kaufmann et al., “Champion-level drone racing using deep reinforcement learning.”

⁵⁴Foehn et al., “AlphaPilot: Autonomous drone racing.”

⁵⁵Tobin et al., “Domain randomization for transferring deep neural networks from simulation to the real world.”

⁵⁶Boneh et al., “Verifiable Delay Functions.”

⁵⁷Pironio et al., “Random numbers certified by Bell’s theorem”; Acín and Masanes, “Certified randomness in quantum physics.”

in the device. **(D) The designer** can introduce a *mapping* bias (the T case); only the *public documentation* of **C3** and **C4**, and the ability to recompute the distribution, make it contestable.

No single layer suffices. A certified QRNG does not protect against an operator who re-plays the draws; a VRF does not protect against a biased *mapping*. Competitive integrity is a *composite* property.

10 Limits

This work has several limits. First, *Quantum Tetris* remains a deliberately minimal case study: its circuits are simulated and its “quantum” backend is a statevector simulator⁵⁸, not a physical device. The instance of layers **C5** and **C6** that we measure rests on commit-reveal and a hash chain; the stronger primitives of Section 6 — full VRF proofs, distributed beacons, verifiable delay functions — are not yet wired in, and their overhead, in particular that of a VDF per draw, is not covered by our measurements. Certified quantum randomness, likewise, remains costly, slow and experimental outside the laboratory⁵⁹. Moreover, transparency raises a tension: publishing the distribution policy may, for some games, facilitate optimization by players; one must then arbitrate between verifiability and design secrecy. Finally, our evaluation concerns only the computation and storage overhead of the audit, on a single case study; it says nothing about players’ perception of fairness, which would call for a user study, nor about behaviour at the scale of a real tournament. These elements constitute direct perspectives.

11 Conclusion

Randomness, in physical games, has a stage: one sees the die, the dice cup, the gesture. The digital game made this stage disappear in favour of an opaque software engine. As long as the game remains private entertainment, this opacity is inconsequential. As soon as it becomes a competition — esports, online games, cyber-physical competitions — it becomes an integrity problem. Through the *Quantum Tetris* case study, and in particular the bias of the T tetromino, we have shown that fairness never reduces to the quality of the entropy source: *entropy is not fairness*. It is decided across the whole chain, from the source to the event, by way of the distribution policy and the *mapping*.

We have proposed to treat this chain as a six-layer infrastructure, and to make it verifiable thanks to existing cryptographic tools — commitment, verifiable random functions, randomness beacons, verifiable delay functions, signed journals. In *Quantum Tetris*, we have implemented its two auditability layers — hash-chained receipts and a commit-reveal journal, verifiable offline — and measured the overhead: on the order of a microsecond per draw, i.e. practically free auditability for a game of this class. Quantum randomness finds there a precise and realistic place: not as a fantasized “quantum” game, but as a physical entropy source, possibly certified, plugged into an interchangeable abstraction. An opaque QRNG remains a black box; a QRNG integrated into a system of proof, public *mapping* and post-match verification becomes a genuine component of competitive integrity. The stage of randomness, lost with the shift to digital, can thus be rebuilt — no longer by a visible object, but by a verifiable protocol.

⁵⁸Roetteler and contributors, *RustQIP: a flexible quantum computing simulator written in Rust*.

⁵⁹Acín and Masanes, “Certified randomness in quantum physics.”

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